

ORGANIZATION OF TRAINING OF PLAYERS

Khadjayev Mansur Kabildjanovich

ASU, Associate professor

Kamolova Mushtariy To'liqinjon qizi

ASU, Master of the 2nd stage

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7451692>

Annotation: *The entire process of sports training can be conditionally divided into education and training, the effective organization of which will help future athletes to strengthen their own physical fitness. The article will talk about the effective organization of training sessions with young players.*

Key words: *sports, football, young players, motor qualities, strength, speed, endurance, dexterity.*

ОРГАНИЗАЦИЯ ТРЕНИРОВОК ИГРОКОВ

Аннотация: *Весь процесс спортивной подготовки можно условно разделить на воспитание и тренировку, эффективная организация которых поможет будущим спортсменам укрепить собственную физическую форму. В статье пойдет речь об эффективной организации тренировочных занятий с молодыми игроками.*

Ключевые слова: *спорт, футбол, юные футболисты, двигательные качества, сила, скорость, выносливость, ловкость.*

INTRODUCTION

The general physical fitness of the player solves the tasks of comprehensively training physical abilities, increasing the overall working capacity. Universal training and exercises from other types of sports, which have a general effect on the body of the participants, are used in this as the main means. In this, the development and strengthening of the musculoskeletal system is achieved by improving the Coordination of movements and increasing the overall level of movement qualities, improving the function of the internal organs and systems.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Many exercises that are used in order to increase overall physical fitness have a comprehensive effect on the body, while each of them is more focused on developing those or those qualities. In particular, long-term jogging in High-Low Places is aimed at developing speed, gymnastic exercises are aimed at increasing agility, while intensive jogging at short distances with greater endurance. These exercises are included in the composition of the training session, while some of them are included in the morning exercises.

The purpose of special physical training is an expression from the development of physical qualities and functional capabilities that are not characteristic only for the player.

It is characterized by the fact that the intensity of the movement that the player performs his activity is constantly changing. High intensity of muscle work-alternating with a decrease in activity and a transition to a relatively calm state. Intensive running, previously thrown, jumps, light running, alternating with stops, the direction of movement, rhythm and pace change. Such activity is associated with the implementation of a certain physical load, which proceeds with serious functional changes in the course of vegetative processes, primarily metabolism, breathing and blood circulation.

RESULTS

However, it should also be taken into account that the player's playing activity does not consist of jumping, running and walking. Being in the conditions of a single tough fight, at the greatest speed and for a long time unusual circumstances (slip, jump, standing on one leg) should not prevent the player from effectively gaining possession of the ball, at the same time solving a complex tactical task. The better players carry the ball, the more thoughtful they act on the pitch, the more interesting the quality of the football performance will be. Therefore, the physical training of the players should be organized in such a way that taking into account the nature of their game activity, give them the basis for improving their technical and tactical skills.

Tirishga with the help of special exercises aimed at developing more specific physical attributes can improve the performance of certain technical priyomes on the go. To do this, as a rule, special exercises are used, which, according to the nature and structure of the performance, are similar to either this or that technical priyom or its individual elements.

In physical training, more and more repeated intervals are used variable, game and competition techniques.

In the annual training cycle, it is recommended to first see general physical training, and then special physical training on this basis. During many years of dealing with football, the ratio of general and special physical preparations, as well as their concrete content, will change towards a gradual increase in the incidence of special preparations for the cultivation of sports skills.

In the general and special physical training of the player, strength, agility, endurance, dexterity are the main ones. The same physical qualities of the moment expressed the level of the player's mobility opportunities.

DISCUSSION

Acquisition and improvement of the ability to implement the main types of voltage, namely static voltage and dynamic voltage, as well as types of directional voltage:

Strengthening all muscle groups in the apparatus of movement in terms of strength harmonic;

Development of the ability to rational use of force under various conditions.

Exercises with increased resistance, that is, exercises that increase strength, are considered a means of training strength. Exercises that increase strength depending on the nature of the resistance are divided into two groups.

1. Exercises that are performed to overcome external resistance. As a rule, as an external resistance, it benefits from:

- A) the weight of the items,
- B) the partner's resistance,
- C) resistance of elastic items,
- G) external environment resistance (eg: running in thick snow).

2. Exercises that are performed with weight gain on their own.

CONCLUSIONS

Also, to lose weight with your own weight will benefit from exercises that are supplemented with the weight of external items. If a person is regularly given a moderate amount of muscle strength, then the strength of the muscle will not grow, and if the amount of tension is very small, then the rate of growth of strength can even decrease. In people who have not seen exercise, their strength begins to decrease if the amount of salt they are showing is less than 20% of the maximum strength. The less the amount of tension, the faster the muscle strength reduction

procedure and the muscle relaxation procedure occur. Even when athletes who are accustomed to the extreme tension of their muscles use relatively large weights, the strength can begin to decrease if the weights are less than usual. Similar features should be taken into account in the preparation of the qualities of the movement of young footballists.

Reference:

1. Akromov R.A. Yosh futbolchilarni tanlab olish va tayyorlash. – T.: Ibn Sino, 1989.
2. Годик М.А. Физическая подготовка футболистов. – М.: Терра-Спорт, Олимпия Пресс, 2006.
3. Курбанов З.А. Организация учебно-тренировочных процессов футболистов в условиях Узбекистана. Учебное пособие. Т., 2000.